

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D9.1

Communication & Dissemination Plan

May 2021

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.

3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UPS	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
RMC-C&E	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UoE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
H2020	Horizon 2020
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
PC	Project Coordinator
TBD	To Be Decided
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as the reference document on the Communication and Dissemination plan of the project, including the targeted audiences, promotional channels and means, for consortium partners (experts and non-experts) to engage, by actively contributing to the communication and dissemination of the project's outputs.

Being a public document, it can also be used by external stakeholder groups as information sheet on the Communication and Dissemination plan of the MES-CoBraD project.

3. Short summary of results

This report mainly outlines the strategy and tools that will be used to implement the MES-CoBraD Communication and Dissemination plan. The major activities to be undertaken and tools to be used for communicating and disseminating the project's results will be explained, alongside with the responsibilities of the consortium and timeline, where possible. It entails how to share the MES-CoBraD scope and results with the appropriate audiences. In doing so, it defines the communication, dissemination and promotional channels and means that will be used for this distribution.

In particular, the promotional means to be used include but are not limited to the MES-CoBraD logo and standard dissemination means, such as those comprising the visual identity of the project; while more specialised means, including articles, reports, scientific publications, infographics, videos, and presentations will be a core aspect of the project's Communication and Dissemination strategy.

The implemented promotional activities so far include the establishment of social media channels for promoting the project scope and activities, the publication of articles in partners' websites, and the design of MES-CoBraD website and promotional material.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will be formally updated in Months 24 and 36 in order to analyse and assess the implemented use of the promotion channels and means and carry out updates/adjustments of the strategy where necessary. It will further consider and align with the project's Stakeholder's engagement strategy to be delivered in M7.

4. Evidence of Accomplishment

This report.

Executive Summary

The main objective of MES-CoBraD (Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders) is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in the Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependences through Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols, in light of the MES-CoBraD Agreement and associated challenges.

Towards this notion, MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

The application of the assessment framework will be implemented through the MES-CoBraD Platform. This platform aims at addressing all the challenges (clinical, research and technological). MES-CoBraD enhances efforts that harmonise and integrate the platform, by maximising individual researchers' impact through collaborative value creation and Open Science practices, including secure data sharing, and sharing of global expertise that is otherwise unavailable in a single institution. The platform will also provide a module (MES-CoBraD Expert System) which aims at improving personalized medicine approaches in real-world practice.

This report mainly outlines the strategy and tools that will be used to implement the MES-CoBraD Communication and Dissemination (C&D) plan. The major activities to be undertaken and tools to be used for communicating and disseminating the project's results will be explained, alongside with the responsibilities of the consortium and timeline, where possible. It entails how to share the MES-CoBraD scope and results with the appropriate audiences. In doing so, it defines the communication, dissemination and promotional channels and means that will be used for this distribution.

In particular, the promotional means to be used are outlined. These include but are not limited to the MES-CoBraD logo and standard dissemination means, such as those are described the visual identity of the project, in D9.3 "Promotional and Informational material"; while more specialised means, including articles, reports, and scientific publications, will be a core aspect of the project's communication and dissemination strategy. Furthermore, project updates will be distributed via the MES-CoBraD newsletters and the partners' newsletters. The use of visual content means, such as infographics, videos, and presentations are also included.

The plan concludes by enlisting the implemented promotional activities so far. These include the establishment of social media channels for promoting the project scope and activities, the publication of articles in partners' websites, and the design of MES-CoBraD website and promotional material.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will be formally updated in Month 24 and 36 to analyse and assess the implemented use of the promotion channels and means and carry out updates or adjustments of the strategy where needed. However, the project's co-creation and co-design approach implies that the CD strategy features far more than the usual CD dynamics, mostly triggered by the engaged stakeholders (WP3) and the Integrated Clinical Research Platform's (WP7) creation and subsequent operation. Consequently, a cross-cutting, uniform and transparent C&D approach will be established with continuous improvements/adjustments.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) project aims at improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in the Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependences through Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols.

Experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, advocacy and marketing & communication across Europe, couple clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

The MES-CoBraD platform will be the next step the project will take towards applying the assessment framework, addressing all present challenges (clinical, research and technological). The secure data sharing provided by the integrated platform will further enable involved scientists in maximising their research impact and expertise sharing, reaching the global community. Furthermore, the MES-CoBraD Expert System module provided by the platform aims to improve personalized medicine approaches in real-world practice.

As noted, the project aims to include in its processes stakeholders across the spectrum of interested actors. These stakeholders are both external and internal, as major groups are also represented by project partners. However, it is acknowledged that the two key groups of MES-CoBraD stakeholders and potential users of the MES-CoBraD Platform, are scientists in the health and social health fields as well as stakeholders working in engineering and computer science at a national, regional and global level. Other groups that should be actively engaged are scientists in general, trade unions, industry associations, business networks, NGOs, and the civil society and general public. Consequently, it is of vital importance that information regarding the project and its outcomes to be disseminated at an early stage, so that all these groups become aware of and then involved in the project's activities early on, so they actively participate in the design of the MES-CoBraD Platform and the co-creation of the scientific processes and results.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will align with the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D3.6), a KPI-driven strategic document that will ensure fostering community engagement and maximizing impact. The Stakeholder Engagement Strategy will build upon the stakeholder groups identified at the level of the proposal and an internal stakeholder analysis, aiming to map the connections, channels and tools project partners already have in use for the engagement of the stakeholders that MES-CoBraD targets.

Given the above, the main purpose of this report is the development of an effective strategy for the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) of information and results of the MES-CoBraD project to the relevant audiences. The C&D strategy addresses the what-to whom-how elements:

- › TO WHOM: Identification of the targeted audiences to which the project will be publicised
- › HOW: Analysis of potential promotional channels and selection of the most appropriate ones according to the targeted audience and the message to be disseminated
- › WHAT: Creation and planning of the CD activities

2 PURPOSE OF THE PLAN

The C&D Plan is a periodic report elaborating on the exact ways, in which the consortium of the MES-CoBraD project can increase its outreach and disseminate the project's results to the relevant audiences. It outlines the strategy and tools that will be employed to implement said strategy. The major activities to be undertaken and tools to be used for communicating and disseminating the project's results will be explained, alongside with the responsibilities of the consortium and timeline, where possible.

This report entails how to share the MES-CoBraD scope and results with the appropriate audiences. In doing so, it defines the communication, dissemination and promotional channels and means that will be employed. It will follow relevant research and novelties in the fields of health and social health as well in computer science and engineering that will help in the modelling process and in achieving the project results. The document lists the different channels needed to reach several relevant target groups, through their preferred communication methods, e.g., a social media pack, relevant conferences, identification of relevant media channels and synergies that could be created with other EU projects or networks. This report also includes the monitoring templates set for events, media work and any other dissemination activity undertaken by the partners. This deliverable will be updated in Month 24 and 36. However, the project's co-creation/co-design approach implies that the CD plan has far more than the usual C&D dynamics, mostly triggered by the evolving stakeholders that will be engaged and the development and operation of the MES-CoBraD Platform. Consequently, a cross-cutting, uniform, and transparent C&D approach will be established with continuous improvements/adjustments.

2.1 THE TWO PILLARS OF PROMOTION: COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION

2.1.1 COMMUNICATION

Communication is the process of informing the widest possible audience, including the media and the public, regarding the project and its results. Its main objective is to reach out to any interested parties and the society and show the impact that MES-CoBraD can achieve. The main audiences targeted for communication purposes are the general public, patients, social health scientists, and civil society.

2.1.2 DISSEMINATION

Dissemination is the process of transferring produced knowledge and results in order to enable others to use and exploit them. Dissemination focuses on the results and outcomes of the initiative, rather than the initiative itself, as well as the ways in which they can be exploited by interested parties. Main audiences suitable for dissemination are the ones who have the ability to use the results in their operation. In the case of MES-CoBraD these are health scientists, doctors, engineers, computer scientists and patients themselves.

2.1.3 TARGETS OF THE C&D STRATEGY

In order to be certain that the results of MES-CoBraD will be communicated and disseminated several targets for most of the C&D activities have been set. The progress towards these targets will be monitored on a regular basis so as to confirm that the project is on track to achieve them or takes the appropriate measures if needed.

The following table presents the targets for each monitored C&D activity. The ways to achieve these targets are described in the document at hand.

Table 1 Targets for each monitored C&D activity

Activity	Target	Means of verification
Development and maintenance of the project website	The project website will spread the objectives and results as widely as possible.	At least 5000 visitors will have accessed the website by the end of the project.
Production of project documentation and printing materials	The project brochure will be a key document, to be disseminated by the Consortium as a whole and by each Consortium partner, as widely as possible.	500 copies of the project brochure will be distributed throughout the project duration. Due to Covid 19 pandemic the project documentation will be also distributed electronically.
Organisation of presentation / feedback sessions (1 per year at major forums or trade shows, relevant to the project theme)	Key stakeholders from Europe and beyond will be invited to presentation/ feedback sessions, to provide the project with their inputs (visions and alternative solutions).	An attendance of 40-70 delegates per event. Due to Covid 19 pandemic online presence will be considered as well.

3 AUDIENCES TO REACH

3.1 CHOICE OF LISTINGS

An understanding of stakeholders' interests, drivers and barriers is essential for effective communication and the prioritisation of tools for communication. Understanding stakeholder motivations will enable the consortium to effectively engage, communicate with, and promote current and future dialogue between different stakeholders. However, whilst communication activities will be tailored for different stakeholder groups, the core scientific content will remain consistent—under no circumstances will the scientific findings of the project be played down, regardless of the interests of certain stakeholder groups.

One of the main goals of the MES-CoBraD C&D Plan is to be used as a feedback mechanism that will enable stakeholders outside the consortium to provide their knowledge to the project and to co-create the MES-CoBraD platform. This will also take place within the scope of WP3 where the relevant stakeholders will be mapped and analysed so they can contribute to the project development through direct engagement activities. It is essential that feedback and suggestions is collected from a variety of individuals with complementary skills and backgrounds, in order to increase the robustness of the project's results.

The target audiences of MES-CoBraD on its initial deployment phase consists of the following groups;

- > TG1: Researchers
- > TG2: Research Producing Organisations (RPOs)
- > TG3: Research funders
- > TG4: Research libraries
- > TG5: Industry
- > TG6: Policy Makers, including public sector entities
- > TG7: Citizen Scientists
- > TG8: Research infrastructures and e-infrastructures
- > TG9: Health Providers, both public and private
- > TG10: Patients, patients advocates
- > TG11: General public

4 PROMOTIONAL CHANNELS & MEANS

In order to deliver the project's messaging to the targeted audiences, the appropriate channels and means will be used. The promotional channels are the ways, or routes, through which the messages may find the desired destinations, i.e., an article in the MES-CoBraD website, a post on social media, the presentation of the project's results in a conference, the participation in an event, etc. A promotional means is the medium that encapsulates the promoted message and is distributed via the channels, i.e., a publication, an infographic, a video, etc.

Each combination of promotional channel and means is unique and serves a different purpose and level of promotion. For example, a scientific publication or a working document is a report with more technical details, aiming to give scientists and researchers a more thorough aspect of an outcome of the action. On the other hand, an infographic is more suitable to feature the fundamentals of the action and its results for a broader audience, while a policy brief is expected to target policymakers.

4.1 POTENTIAL PROMOTIONAL CHANNELS

4.1.1 THE MES-COBRA D WEBSITE

The MES-CoBraD Website (<http://www.mes-cobrad.eu/>) will serve as a one-stop shop and will be in the centre of the promotional process. It will be used for both pillars of promotion and will contain (or be linked to) every promotional material of the action. The website's development is currently in progress and will consist of several informational webpages, mainly information about the action (concept, objectives and work structure) as well as pages showcasing specific activities (e.g., the organisation of events), or major outcomes, namely reports, publications, infographics, etc. The website will also promote transparency of the project's scientific capabilities and processes, assumptions and results, by providing background information and a direct link to the MES-CoBraD Platform. It is worth mentioning that the MES-CoBraD will be co-designed by the relevant stakeholders in order to increase its usability and usage. More on the creation of the MES-CoBraD platform will be available in the upcoming respective report specifically "D.7.2 MES-CoBraD platform Release 1.00". Finally, it will use responsive web-design enabling access from different screen sizes/platforms of desktops and smartphones. More on the website will be available in the upcoming respective report, "D9.2 Website".

In order to increase the visibility and traffic to the website, as well as the number of downloads of the reports an excessive campaign will be implemented via the other communication and dissemination channels (i.e., social media, blog articles, communication lists, etc.), as well as relying on cross-promotion on behalf of the partners, through their own channels and platforms. Moreover, several opinion blog articles containing relevant keywords will be posted on the website in order to boost search engine optimisation and achieve showcase of the website in the top search lists of search engine results for relevant queries.

4.1.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media provide an online platform for everyone who has internet access to exchange opinions, knowledge, and expertise. Thus, it is a very effective medium for organisations to implement marketing and promotional campaigns. In MES-CoBraD, it is envisaged that social media will be used in order to promote the action and its results to every possible stakeholder, not only for communication purposes but also for dissemination and exploitation reasons. Social Media presence and activity is also very well suited to indirect promotion and dissemination activities, as linked subjects that are being discussed/shared could allow for the introduction of the MES-CoBraD project in general and its relevant, specific messages in particular. This is of key importance especially at the initial stages of the project, when an initial "follower club" should be established.

The following table presents the aim and reason for the three key social media channels.

Table 2 Aim & purpose per Social Media channel

Social Media Channel	Purpose	Plan
Twitter	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific community, the health department community and the civil society.	At least 1 weekly update on current affairs and project's progress.
LinkedIn	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific and policymaking community.	At least 1 monthly update Ad hoc posts on project's progress.
Facebook	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the society	At least 1 weekly update on current affairs.
ResearchGate	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific community	At least 1 monthly update Ad hoc posts on project's progress

Twitter

Twitter¹ is an online social networking service on which users post and interact with short messages (less than 280 characters). It is ideal for short announcements of the action's outcomes and will be used ad hoc. Via its account in Twitter MES-CoBraD is envisaged to reach a wide variety of audiences suitable primarily for communication and dissemination purposes.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn² is a business and employment-oriented social network allowing individuals and organisations to promote their professional progress and outcomes. The MES-CoBraD page in LinkedIn will be used to target more specialised audiences within the framework of dissemination and exploitation and will be updated at least once in a month.

Facebook

Facebook³ is a social networking app for sharing photos and videos with other user and it is ideal for communicating with members of the general public. Via its channel MES-CoBraD will post pictures on health issues which are relevant to the brain disorders issues and will communicate its scope and objective to the wider public.

ResearchGate

ResearchGate⁴ is a social network for scientists and researchers to share papers, ask and answer questions, and find collaborators. Through this channel, MES-CoBraD will reach out to the scientific community in order to distribute its scientific publications and other reports.

Youtube

YouTube will be used in order to host and promote the MES-CoBraD videos, which would be of wide variety, such as interviews, explanatory videos, etc. The MES-CoBraD YouTube channel will be created as soon as the 1st video is created.

¹ <https://twitter.com/MESCoBraD>

² <https://www.linkedin.com/in/mes-cobrad-4b445a212/>

³ <https://www.facebook.com/mescobrad/>

⁴ <https://www.researchgate.net/>

4.1.3 BLOGS AND NEWS WEBSITES

In the following sections, a list of high-calibre media websites, through which it would be beneficial for MES-CoBraD to be communicated, is presented. These websites often feature opinion articles from external sources in their “Opinion” columns, so it is possible to include an article regarding MES-CoBraD as well. However, it is worth mentioning that this is an indicative, non-exhaustive list which may be modified if it is considered necessary.

EC website (CORDIS)

MES-CoBraD will be in close co-operation with the departments of the European commission and will update the cordis webpage⁵ with its progress.

EC Success Stories Webpage

It is envisaged that MES-CoBraD will publish a couple of articles featuring its outcomes via the EC Success Stories webpage⁶. These articles are expected to increase the participation of experts in the stakeholder groups.

Neuroscience News

Neuroscience News⁷ is a website focused on neuroscience and MES-CoBraD may share the projects research development and disseminate results and news.

Association of Alternative News media

AAN⁸ aims to strengthen alternative journalism through advocacy and education. This platform could provide an opportunity for MES-CoBraD to further communicate its goals and results.

Neurology Today

Neurology Today⁹ is the official news source of the American Academy of Neurology and MES-CoBraD partners could expand the project’s reach by publishing.

BMC Public Health

BMC Public Health¹⁰ is an open access, peer-reviewed journal that considers articles on the epidemiology of disease and the understanding of all aspects of public health. During the projects lifecycle the possibility to publish on BMC may be investigated.

JAMA Network

Jama Network¹¹ with a vast assembly of Medical Journals and a specific one for neurology (JAMA Neurology) may provide another platform for MES-CoBraD’s CD targets.

4.1.4 JOURNALS

Research*eu

Research*eu Results magazine¹² covers topics of research interest in the EU. Through this channel,

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/965422>

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories>

⁷ <https://neurosciencenews.com/>

⁸ <https://aan.org/>

⁹ <https://journals.lww.com/neurotodayonline/pages/default.aspx>

¹⁰ <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/>

¹¹ <https://jamanetwork.com/>

¹² https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html

outcomes of MES-CoBraD will be communicated and disseminated to scientists, policymakers in the EU and Member States (MS), and the general public.

Science, Technology, & Human Values

For more than forty years Science, Technology, & Human Values¹³ has provided the forum for cutting-edge research and debate in the field of science and technology studies. ST&HV is a double-blind peer-reviewed, bi-monthly, international, interdisciplinary journal containing research, analyses and commentary on the development and dynamics of science and technology, including their relationship to politics, society and culture. The journal publishes work from scholars in a diverse range of disciplines across the social sciences.

Ethics and Information Technology

The journal¹⁴ is a peer-reviewed journal dedicated to advancing the dialogue between moral philosophy and the field of information and communication technology (ICT). The journal aims to foster and promote reflection and analysis which is intended to make a constructive contribution to answering the ethical, social and political questions associated with the adoption, use, and development of ICT.

4.1.5 ONLINE COLLABORATION PLATFORMS

Capacity4Dev

Capacity4Dev is the European Commission's knowledge sharing platform for development cooperation aiming to improve capacity building. This is done among others by enabling cross-learning between practitioners from EU institutions and other organisations. The platform has over 25,000 members who share, learn and collaborate on the fields of sustainable development. This channel is ideal for dissemination and exploitation purposes since its members are scientists, industrialists, EU staff, and sustainable development professionals from EU MS, policymakers at EU & global level, as well as civil societies.

AI4EU

Artificial Intelligence for Europe¹⁵ is the first European Artificial Intelligence On-Demand Platform and Ecosystem with the support of the European Commission under the H2020 programme. AI4EU is a large European ecosystem spanning the 28 countries to facilitate collaboration between all Europeans actors in AI. MES-CoBraD may demonstrate the capabilities of the platform to be developed and further communicate the project goals and research results.

European Academy of Neurology

EAN¹⁶ is a non-profit, independent organization that aims to promote quality in neurology and bring together Europe's best clinicians, educators and scientists in the field to foster and support the development of neurological excellence in Europe and across the world. MES-CoBraD with its unique approach on improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes on people with CoBraD may approach EAN in an effort to further communicate the project results.

4.1.6 PUBLISHING PLATFORMS

Open Research Europe

Open Research Europe (ORE)¹⁷ is an innovative open access publishing platform for the publication of

¹³ <http://journals.sagepub.com/home/sth>

¹⁴ <http://www.springer.com/computer/swe/journal/10676>

¹⁵ <https://www.ai4eu.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://www.ean.org/>

¹⁷ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding that makes it easy for Horizon 2020 beneficiaries to comply with the open access terms of their funding and offers researchers a publishing venue to share their results and insights rapidly and facilitate open, constructive research discussion. The use of this platform will enable MES-CoBraD involved researchers to publish their research results fast and provide an open peer review that will enhance the project's impact and reach. ORE uses an open research publishing model that supports reproducibility, transparency and impact.

The Innovation Radar

The Innovation Radar¹⁸ is European Commission's data-driven method focused on the identification of high potential innovations and the key innovators behind them in EU-funded Research and Innovation projects. Innovation Radar has the goal of creating a steady flow of promising tech companies that can scale up into future industrial champions. MES-CoBraD through the use of the Innovation Radar will be able to further enhance the role of its platform and provide insight on the projects scope to interested stakeholders and medical industry related companies.

OpenAIRE portal

OpenAIRE¹⁹ is a science-related portal, the mission of which is to provide unlimited, barrier-free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. The use of OpenAIRE will enable MES-CoBraD, on one hand, to report more effectively and efficiently the scientific, and other, outcomes of the action and, on the other, to reach a wide community of scientists, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in EU-funded research in general.

Zenodo

Zenodo²⁰ is a general purpose open access repository developed by CERN within the framework of OpenAIRE, welcoming all science information around the globe, i.e., research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts from every discipline. MES-CoBraD will create a community under Zenodo, in order to provide its outputs in open access and disseminate them to appropriate audiences at the same time. More on the management, processing and maintainability of the action's data and outcomes will be available in the upcoming respective report, "D2.2 Data management plan".

4.1.7 DATA REPOSITORIES- DATABASES

Although MES-CoBraD will also act as a data repository for study and automatic diagnosis, the following repositories will be considered aiming towards providing access to the scientific community on the project's data and enhancing the project's reach.

Data Europa

Data Europa²¹ is the point of access to public data published by the EU institutions, agencies and other bodies. The portal is a key instrument of the EU open data strategy with its Information available for commercial or non-commercial purposes. MES-CoBraD could benefit from the established audience of this repository to enhance its presence in the scientific community.

G-Node

G-Node²² is a web-based secure repository store that you can reach from everywhere that will enable MES-CoBraD sharing data with collaborators or publishing to the greater scientific community.

¹⁸ <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/>

²¹ <https://data.europa.eu/en>

²² <https://gin.g-node.org/>

EBRAINS

EBRAINS²³ provides digital tools and services which can be used to address challenges in brain research and brain-inspired technology development. The tools provided by EBRAINS aim in assisting researchers to collect, analyse, share, and integrate brain data, and to perform modelling and simulation of brain function, and an interaction with MES-CoBraD data may raise awareness on the projects progress and results.

EU Health Data Space

Depending on the level of maturity of the EU Health Data Space²⁴, it may be considered for sharing data with it. The creation of a European Data Space is one of the priorities of the Commission 2019-2025, including the health sector. A common European Health Data Space will promote better exchange and access to different types of health data (electronic health records, genomics data, data from patient registries etc.), not only to support healthcare delivery (so-called primary use of data) but also for health research and health policy making purposes (so-called secondary use of data). MES-CoBraD will investigate the possibilities to integrate its repositories with the service, or individually share data with it.

4.1.8 PARTNERS' WEBSITES/BLOGS

Most partners have websites featuring news on their research activities. In these websites, articles on the progress of MES-CoBraD, as well as announcements on recent reports or upcoming events, have been and will further be published. More particularly, the partners' websites are the NTUA²⁵ partner which is the coordinator of the project, the NIA's²⁶ webpage, the VUB-LSTS²⁷ webpage, the UPS²⁸ university website, the KCL²⁹ website's homepage that features recent news on research progress and upcoming events, while a dedicated webpage for specifically promoting projects' results is also available, SIMAVI³⁰ webpage, the LIBER³¹ website including a specific page dedicated on MES-CoBraD information and news targeting the research library community³², the ENG³³ webpage, the HOLISTIC³⁴ webpage dedicated to news at which developments on MES-CoBraD could be featured, the EVOLUTION³⁵ webpage, the University of Edinburg³⁶ webpage, the CyberEthics Lab³⁷. webpage.

4.1.9 PARTNERS' JOURNALS

LIBER Quarterly

LIBER Quarterly³⁸ is the peer reviewed, open access journal of LIBER, the association of European research libraries. It covers thematises across disciplines that are relevant for research librarians and researchers across Europe. As per its scope, it is "intended as a bridge between the scholars of the LIS departments and the practitioners in university and research libraries. It achieves this by publishing not

²³ <https://ebrains.eu/service/share-data/>

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/health/ehealth/dataspace_en

²⁵ <http://www.epu.ntua.gr>

²⁶ www.nioa.gr

²⁷ <https://lsts.research.vub.be>

²⁸ <https://www.uu.se/>

²⁹ www.klc.ac.uk/ioppn

³⁰ www.simavi.ro

³¹ libereurope.eu

³² <https://libereurope.eu/project/mes-cobrad/>

³³ [Large Enterprise](http://LargeEnterprise)

³⁴ <https://www.holisticsa.gr/articles-3-col>

³⁵ <https://www.evolutionprojects.gr/>

³⁶ <https://ghpu.sps.ed.ac.uk/>

³⁷ www.cyberethicslab.com

³⁸ <https://www.libquarterly.eu/>

only theoretical contributions, but also descriptions of examples of good practices".

4.1.10 PARTNERS' EVENTS

4.1.10.1 MES-CoBraD Workshops

Workshops are small interactive events held to achieve a specific objective. A workshop could be used to get feedback from users on the proposed solution or to get feedback from expert on a particular issue. Within the framework of MES-CoBraD, in the first year all partners will organize and/or attend to at least three stakeholder events and workshops which will be addressing the target communities and the end-users of the MES-CoBraD platform. In the second year of the project, all partners will organize and/or attend to at least five stakeholder events and workshops. Finally, in the third year of the MES-CoBraD project all partners will organize and/or attend to at least five stakeholder events and workshops. There will be a planned participation for all the partners in forthcoming EU Conferences and Workshops. Workshops, as other events, take into account health and travel restrictions related to COVID19, hence they are taking place as online events for the first period of the project, aiming to expand to hybrid and/or face-to-face formats later in the project.

4.1.11 EXTERNAL EVENTS

In order to effectively promote MES-CoBraD, partners will be encouraged and assisted in the participation in events organised by organisations outside the consortium. This includes the participation in events organised by the European Commission and in other international conferences and workshops in the respective fields so as to keep updated the scientific community, universities, research centres, industry, the EC, policymakers, health scientists and other interested groups. It is envisaged that each partner will participate in at least one event per year.

4.1.11.1 Scientific Conferences

MES-CoBraD partners will participate in scientific conferences, in order to disseminate the action to the scientific community by presenting the action's outcomes in a scientific manner.

4.1.11.2 General Conferences

Along the duration of MES-CoBraD project, the partners will take place in some conferences. Those are ICHA 2021: Healthcare and Analytics Conference; ICDHW 2021: Digital Health and Wellness Conference; ICHS 2021: Healthcare Systems Conference; International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Communication Engineering (ICAICE); International Conference on General Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (ICGAIR). The annual LIBER Conference, bringing together around 450 librarians and relevant stakeholders across disciplines from around Europe, as well as the LIBER mid-term event will also be used as venues for promotion and engagement. The Society for Philosophy and Technology (SPT) conference. SPT is an independent international organization that encourages, supports, and facilitates philosophically significant considerations of technology.

4.1.11.3 Workshops

Several workshops organised by external organisations could be used so as to promote MES-CoBraD. A typical example are several networking events, which are organised for networking among EU-funded projects.

4.1.11.4 Other Events

Apart from conferences and workshops, other events offer opportunities of collaboration with stakeholders, who might be interested in MES-CoBraD's results. These could include commercial exhibitions, anniversary celebration events, etc.

4.1.11.5 Synergies

Creation of synergies with other relevant actions, either funded under Horizon2020 and Horizon Europe or not, is of great importance since it bears many advantages. More particularly, clustering activities increase the outreach potential of the action concepts and raise awareness among a broader spectrum of stakeholders. The plan for creating synergies and promoting collaborations with other projects and initiatives is an important milestone for the project, "MS3 - Identification of opportunity-based promotional activities", the outcomes of which will be presented in detail in the respective report, "D9.8: Final report on opportunity-based promotional activities". Other tools used for clustering activities will be social media and the website. More particularly, the website will contain an External Resources page, listing existing works of other platforms and related projects.

4.1.11.6 Horizon Result Booster

Horizon Result Booster³⁹ is a new package of specialised services to maximise the impact of R&I public investment and further amplify the added value of a HORIZON 2020 funded project. We consider using the services of this platform for the envelopment of the C&D strategy of MES-CoBraD project since it could speed up the process of creating an impact and provide valuable support to remove bottlenecks. Horizon Result Booster may be equally used in the Exploitation strategy in parallel to the C&D strategy, as it will be described in the D9.5 "Business and Exploitation Plan - v1".

4.1.11.7 Promotional Means

In order to promote MES-CoBraD several promotional materials encapsulating the action's scope, objectives, and expected results are envisaged. Moreover, all the promotional material that will be used will have a simple but distinctive visual identity which has already been created so as to have a consistent and systematic way.

4.1.11.8 Logo

To create identity within the consortium and to support "brand recognition" the MES-CoBraD logo was created and will be used in all promotional material. More on the logo can be found in the report "D9.3: Promotional and informational material".

4.1.11.9 Leaflet

A promotional leaflet featuring a short project description for dissemination among stakeholders, at conferences and to other interested parties, has been created. In particular, the leaflet briefly describes the project's aims, objectives, contents, expected results, consortium and contact details, and will soon be available in all languages of the consortium members. More on the leaflet can be found in the report "D9.3: Promotional and informational material".

4.1.11.10 Poster

A publicity poster regarding MES-CoBraD was designed and printed in order to promote the action in events organised by the partners or hosted by other relevant organisations. Specifically, the poster briefly describes the action's aims, objectives, contents, expected results, consortium and contact details. More on the poster can be found in the report "D9.3: Promotional and informational material".

4.1.11.11 MES-CoBraD Presentation

A standard presentation containing basic information about MES-CoBraD has been produced in order to be used by the partners for dissemination purposes at relevant events. It is envisaged that the presentation will be regularly updated and adapted by the partners on an ad hoc basis, according to the type and size of audience/events where the project will be presented. More on the presentation can be

³⁹ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

found in the report “D9.3: Promotional and informational material”.

4.1.11.12 *Articles*

Appropriate articles according to the targeted audience will be disseminated via the aforementioned promotional channels (websites, blogs, etc.). Depending on the desired outcome, these articles may focus on MES-CoBraD and its societal impacts in general or be more specific by promoting individual project outcomes.

4.1.11.13 *Reports*

MES-CoBraD will produce a total of 56 publicly distributed reports incorporating the results of the implemented research. These reports will be available at the project’s website and will be further promoted via social media, newsletters, and other dissemination channels.

4.1.11.14 *Working Documents*

Working documents focus on the output deliverables of MES-CoBraD, which will be consolidated and available in a series of branded reports. Working documents will consist of the main points of the deliverables and will give the main outcomes of the implemented research. They will be distributed in organised events either as hardcopies, or preferably in digital format.

4.1.11.15 *Scientific Publications*

Scientific publications are one of the keys means of disseminating the project’s results to the research community and providing the scientific credibility for the project’s work. Scientific publications and policy papers will be published in open access, high-quality, peer-reviewed journals and platforms (e.g., ORE), so as to ensure that the project and its results are made known to the public at large. NTUA will draft a list of topics where published articles would be valuable and journals that might be suitable. The consortium members will sign an agreement for commonly sharing all material produced under MES-CoBraD including scientific publications financed by the project through appropriate open access schemes and archiving it to appropriate repositories.

4.1.12 NEWSLETTERS & PRESS RELEASES

4.1.12.1 *MES-CoBraD Newsletters*

The MES-CoBraD newsletters are used to announce the project, develop a profile, and give regular updates on its progress and developments. The newsletters will be creative making sure that all target audiences know how the project is progressing. A regular electronic newsletter will be issued providing information on the project development and events on a six-monthly basis. The Newsletter will incorporate inputs from all partners on progress and key outcomes of the project. Its key aim is to raise awareness about the ongoing work of the action and its relevance to policymaking at EU and national level. The Newsletter will be sent to all MES-CoBraD stakeholders as identified throughout the project, as long as they have provided their consent to subscribe to the newsletter. The subscription process complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which came into force in May 2018. In order to include a person to the newsletter mailing list, a freely given, informed and explicit consent has been given specifically to receive the MES-CoBraD newsletter, while the possibility of withdrawing the consent is clearly explained. Consents are provided either by filling in an online subscription form, by writing the email in the participants list in an organised event, or by direct email in case of personal contacts. It must be noted that these ways may be updated, as necessary.

It is envisaged that up to 10 e-newsletters will be developed, which will regularly disseminate the project’s achievements. The e-newsletters will be developed in English and be translated in all project languages. The e-newsletters in addition to being published on the project’s website, so that these are readily accessible by all the target groups across Europe, will be distributed by email to public authorities and other relevant stakeholders in each participating country. The effectiveness of the newsletters’ impact

will be evaluated by a respective tool and reports, including openings, clicks and list of recipients. Moreover, occasionally press releases may be circulated to various stakeholders and interested parties in case there is a specific need. It is envisaged that at least six press releases will be circulated in non-academic sources.

4.1.12.2 *Infographics*

Due to the information overload, which is a typical characteristic of the latest years, it is very important to use visual means of promotion such as infographics, videos, and presentations. Infographics may be produced during the MES-CoBraD implementation phase, to present various project outcomes.

Appropriately designed infographics will be used to convey to health scientists and other relevant stakeholders the MES-CoBraD results through comprehensive visual representations. Infographics make broad or complex ideas more distilled and simplified and are more eye-catching than printed words, since they combine images, colours, movement, and content.

4.1.12.3 *Videos*

Videos can be used in order to disseminate the MES-CoBraD results in a more effective way to appropriate audiences. It is envisaged that a total of three videos targeted at health scientists and other stakeholder groups will be produced and circulated during the project's lifetime. The production of videos will be used to present the project's activities in English, with subtitled version for all the project's languages. It is foreseen that 5 videos will be produced within the project phase.

4.1.12.4 *Presentations*

Partners participating in external events are highly encouraged to deliver presentations on the project's scope, objectives, and expected (or already extracted) results. It is envisaged that more than twenty Internet presentations in academic conferences in at least ten European and non-European countries will be delivered within the project's lifetime.

5 IMPLEMENTED ACTIVITIES

5.1 SOCIAL MEDIA

The online presence of MES-CoBraD has already been established in Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. In particular, in Twitter an official MES-CoBraD account has been created while the #MES-CoBraD hashtag is used in every post regarding the action. Moreover, in LinkedIn an organisation webpage has been created in order to disseminate the MES-CoBraD results. Finally, in Facebook account has been created in order to promote the project to the general public. Both direct promotion of the project's beginning (Kick-off meeting, 1st Newsletter, etc.) and a broad, indirect promotion/engagement campaign has been ongoing; see some examples below.

5.2 PARTNERS' WEBSITES

An article on the implementation of the MES-CoBraD's kick-off meeting was published in NTUA's website⁴⁰ describing the project, its objective, and the organisation of the kick-off. A Facebook post⁴¹ on MES-CoBraD was published NTUA's Facebook page as well on the institution's participation on the project. NTUA twitted⁴² as well on the project's developments prior to the kick off meeting. In the HOLISTIC news webpage one article featuring MES-CoBraD has already been published⁴³, on the project and the role HOLISTIC will play in it.

LIBER has created a specific page⁴⁴, dedicated to MES-CoBraD on its website, as space to share project news and other information (e.g. events, materials, etc) targeting research libraries and relevant stakeholders. Regular information about the project will be shared on LIBER's social media, internal mailing lists and LIBER Insider, a monthly mailing targeting the LIBER community.

5.3 MES-COBRA D NEWSLETTERS

The first newsletter of MES-CoBraD will be launched in June 2021 promoting the project's objectives and scope, also featuring the action's Kick-off Meeting.

5.4 ORGANIZATION OF EVENTS

5.4.1 KICK-OFF MEETING, 12-13 APRIL 2021, ATHENS, GREECE

MES-CoBraD's Kick-off Meeting was successfully remotely organised via Teams, on the 13th of April 2021. Participants had the opportunity to remotely meet with each other, overview the project's expectations and discuss the challenges of the forthcoming tasks. In total 45 people from 9 countries attended the meeting. The event featured several insightful presentations by highly qualified experts setting the tone for the actions that will follow during the coming months, as well as the strategic planning for the duration of the project.

5.4.2 OTHER EVENTS

The project management team will consider potential COVID-19 related barriers in the delivery of activities, to prevent delays or poor quality. The current health situation will be closely monitored. More specifically, when it comes to events, the project made a provision of more online activities that face-to-face ones, in order to encourage social distancing. Appropriate platforms/tools for engaging activities will

⁴⁰ <https://www.epu.ntua.gr/node/449>

⁴¹ <https://www.facebook.com/epu.ntua.gr/posts/230918048821423>

⁴² https://twitter.com/DSS_Lab/status/1381525044044554242

⁴³ <https://holisticsa.gr/projects/h2020-MES-CoBraD>

⁴⁴ <https://libereurope.eu/project/mes-cobrad/>

be used for this purpose.

7 NEXT STEPS / CONCLUSIONS

In the following subsections, the CDE activities scheduled for the 1st year of the project are presented. In particular, a detailed promotional campaign according to each task has been structured.

7.1 WEBSITE

In order to increase the website's traffic and establish a loyal audience, a blog section will be created including articles which will analyse the initial results of the research carried out and the structure of the MES-CoBraD platform. This will result in the improvement of the website's content and its search engine optimisation (SEO). Furthermore, these articles will include links to appropriate sections of the website, i.e., the Material section, etc. This will reduce the bounce rate since visitors will be motivated to explore more webpages. It is envisaged that for the upcoming year at least 4 to 6 articles will be published in the MES-CoBraD blog section.

7.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

In the upcoming period, the promotional campaign in social media will be more intense, so that it will increase both the project's visibility in social media and the traffic to the website. In particular, the campaign will include 1 to 3 posts per week in each social media account. This increase in the social media presence will support the overcoming of the remaining implications of Covid-19.

7.3 ONLINE MEDIA

The presence of MES-CoBraD in online media will be increased in the upcoming period. Specifically, it is envisaged that a total of 5 to 10 articles in external online media will be published. This will lead to an increased traffic to the website, as well as optimisation of the website's SEO since there will be more backlinks towards the website. These articles will include topics regarding the MES-CoBraD research and deliverables, as well as the development of the AI Algorithm. Furthermore, representatives of the project will give interviews to well-known media relevant to the project's scope.

7.4 PARTNER'S WEBSITE / BLOGS

In the following period, a series of articles are expected to be published on partners' websites and/or blogs. These articles will focus on the project's outcomes and progress, as well as the partner's contribution. The objective of this promotional activity is to increase the project's visibility as well as the website's traffic and SEO. It is intended that at least one article will be included in each partner's website, while ideally a total of 4 articles per partner are desired. The increase of promotional articles in partners' websites and blogs will support the C&D strategy and help achieve our goals.

7.5 NEWSLETTERS & PRESS RELEASES

The circulation of project newsletters and press releases will be enhanced in the upcoming year in order to increase the project's visibility, the website's traffic, the dissemination in the scientific community and the attendance of events organised by MES-CoBraD. It is envisaged that a total of 4 to 6 newsletters will be circulated in the upcoming year, as well as 4 to 6 press releases.

7.6 C&D PLAN UPDATE

The CDE Plan will be further updated in report D9.6 "Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities Report and Plan", which will be finalised in March 2023. The situation will be reassessed at that time and appropriate actions will be explored and defined.

